

MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES ASSESSMENT: A KEY IN ALIGNING DIFFERENTIATED ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to assess the Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School and to align teachers' classroom activities to the needs, interests and strength of the learners. Thus, this study employed a Descriptive Quantitative type of research and used standardized assessment tool in gathering data. Based on results of the study, it was found out that female respondents have the larger number compared to male respondents. And both male and female respondents dominate *Naturalistic Intelligence*. On the other hand, section Gumamela has the highest number of respondents when data is grouped according to section. Moreover, *Naturalistic Intelligence* dominates in all section except section SSP which dominates *Interpersonal Intelligence*. The result declares that most of the grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School were interested in classes and activities with more involvement with surroundings and environment. Apart from that, *Musical Intelligence* got the lowest rank in both section Daisy & Cattleya, *Visual/Spatial Intelligence* in both section Gumamela & Vanda and *Intrapersonal Intelligence* in both section SSP & STVEP. Henceforth, classroom facilitators are encouraged to prepare exercises according to the needs, interests, strength, and intelligences of the learners to align differentiated activities. Moreover, classroom activities must conform to the strong intelligences of the learners to address diversity.

Keywords: Multiple Intelligences, Differentiated Activities, Assessment, Learning Style

INTRODUCTION

Every student has their own ability and learning styles in coping with the teaching and learning process. Some other students tend to answer activities in a different way and some other students opt to answer activities. This observation manifests that learner diverse from each other.

Finding strategies to meet diverse learners' needs and learning styles is a challenge for many teachers. In turn, this enables each child to study in a way that is related to his or her abilities, resolving the age-old conundrum of how to accommodate individual student variances (Nolen 2003).

On the other hand, teachers are looking for a different pedagogy in teaching that suits the needs of the learners and to achieve the intended learning outcomes in pursuing quality Education. Thus, every classroom activity should anchor on the necessary needs of the learners as being observed the Learner-Centered Classroom. The Learner-Centered is an approach that place the students at the center. This further means that most of the work and activities are done by the students and the teacher will act as the facilitator inside the classroom.

In a third-year pharmacotherapy course, the learner-centered approach was successful in boosting several areas of motivation and learning strategies. Particularly, it appears that the learner-centered approach enhances students' attitudes, intrinsic motivation, and critical-thinking skills. Additionally, students stated that the learner-centered strategy improved their learning (Cheang 2009).

Moreover, the Department of Education encouraged all the teachers to prepare and deliver classroom activities in different ways or the so-called differentiated Activity. This differentiated activity purposely designed to address the needs of the students particularly in manifesting collaborative and participative attitude but sadly teachers may face difficult in preparing activities that will really suit the needs and interest of the learners.

Anent to this, classroom teachers hardly identify and determine the differences of the learners specifically in classroom participation and collaboration. Differentiated were given, but teachers don not have knowledge if the differentiated activities were suit to the needs of the learners. In so, diversity of the learners should be determined based on the theory of Howard Gardner's Multiple Intelligences.

The seven intelligences are present in every person at birth. All kids will nevertheless enter the classroom with various combinations of developed intelligences. Each child will therefore have an own set of intellectual talents and shortcomings. These sets indicate whether a student will find it simple (or difficult) to learn material when it is presented in a specific way. This is referred to as a learning style in most contexts.

Thus, this study was conducted to assess the learners' intelligences prior to the giving of differentiated activities to address learner's diversity.

This literature review investigates the necessity for "differentiated" or academically relevant instruction. It provides theoretical and empirical support for customizing instruction in mixed-ability classroom settings based on a paradigm of addressing student preparation, interest, and learning profile (Tomlinson et al. 2003).

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 learners of Tampilisan National High School in aligning the Differentiated activities amid Pandemic.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Grade 7 Students of Tampilisan National High School in terms of;
 - a. Sex,
 - b. Section?
2. What are the dominant Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School in terms of;
 - a. Sex,
 - b. Section?
3. Based on the result, what differentiated activities shall be given to the Grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School in terms of;
 - a. Section?
4. Based on the result, what school program/strategy shall be proposed to align the differentiated activities to the needs and interest of the Learner?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed Descriptive Quantitative Research with the aid of the standardized Assessment for the students. To determine the abilities, interests, strength, weaknesses, and intelligences of the learners. The Assessment/Questionnaire is standardized from Multiple Intelligences Test for Children by Tara Kunesh. This design is appropriate since the study aimed to assess the intelligences of the learners and described its interests to properly aligned differentiated classroom activities.

Research Participants

The Respondents of this study were the Grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School, School year 2022-2023. On the other hand, a total enumeration or One hundred percent (100%) of the students was used. Tampilisan National high School composes of 6 sections. (1) Cattleya with 39 respondents, (2) Daisy with 52, (3) Gumamela with 53, (4) SSP with 51 respondents (5) section STVEP with 51 and (6) Vanda with 39 respondents. To sum up, there were 285 Grade 7 students participated in the study, 134 were male respondents and 151 were female respondents. Moreover,

Research Instrument

The Multiple Intelligences Test for Children by Tara Kunesh was administered by the Researcher to the respondents. Thus, the assessment tool was translated in Filipino to be more understandable to the respondents. Thus, the translated assessment was submitted to the panel who are experts in language for validity and promptness of the translation.

On the other hand, the assessment/Questionnaire checklist was composed of two (2) parts. The first part was the profile of the respondents particular on the sex assigned by birth and the section. And the second part was the Multiple Intelligences Worksheet which composes of eight

(8) sections comprises the eight Multiple Intelligences of Howard Gardner. Aside from that, a scoring table was also used in determining the result on the abilities of the respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study follows the ethical standard of research. An approval sheet was submitted to the School Principal for approval and another letter was given to the Class Adviser for the schedule of gathering data. Aside from that, a research form prescribed by the Department of Education was accomplished by the researchers prior to the administration of the study. Lastly, the responses of the respondents were treated with utmost confidentiality.

Data Analysis

After gathering, the researchers tally the gathered data and the result of the scoring table. Frequency count, percentage distribution, was used to come up with an apt analysis and interpretation of the data gathered. Apart from that, a frequency distribution graph was also used in presenting data result.

RESULTS

Table 1: Suggested Differentiated Activities of the Grade 7 learners according to section.

Section	Strong Activities <i>Based on the highest 3 dominant Multiple Intelligences</i>	Weak Activities <i>Based on the Lowest dominant Multiple Intelligences</i>
Daisy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cleaning activities in community areas •Walks in natural environments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listen to musical pieces • Music appreciation activities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show videos, films or documentaries related to nature • Story reading • Oral presentations • Speech competitions (speeches in 3 minutes) • Use of concept maps • Activities that involve the use of maps • Pictionary game • Activities using Minecraft 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Play instruments • Create songs and rhythms • Measure the musical time using the metronome • Create melodies to learn concepts • Provide classroom spaces for individual study • Activities related to the theme of self-esteem • Self-taught readings <p>Application of learning centre's</p>
Cattleya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Story reading • Oral presentations • Speech competitions (speeches in 3 minutes) • Reflective diaries writing • Perform podcasts on studied topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listen to musical pieces • Music appreciation activities • Play instruments • Use of concept maps • Activities that involve the use of maps • Pictionary game
Gumamela	<p>Use pets or plants during discussion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make orchards or gardens • Cleaning activities in community areas • Listen to musical pieces • Music appreciation activities • Play instruments • Create songs and rhythms • Story reading • Oral presentations • Speech competitions (speeches in 3 minutes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of concept maps • Activities that involve the use of maps • Pictionary game • Use of 1 minute reflection period • Activities that integrate the independent study • Provide classroom spaces for individual study • Self-taught readings
SSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of board games • Roleplay activities • Peer tutoring • Creation of academic clubs • Community support activities • Use pets or plants during discussion • Make orchards or gardens • Cleaning activities in community areas • Walks in natural environments • Story reading • Oral presentations • Speech competitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of 1 minute reflection period • Activities that integrate the independent study • Use of puzzles • Solution of verbal problems • Use of the scientific method
STVEP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use pets or plants during discussion • Make orchards or gardens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of 1 minute reflection period • Activities that integrate the independent study • Use of puzzles

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cleaning activities in community areas • Walks in natural environments • Craft use • Learning by discovery • Use of Legos • Body movement activities (dance, pantomime, role play, acting) • Use of board games • Roleplay activities • Peer tutoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solution of verbal problems • Use of the scientific method • Use of Socratic questions (maieutic)
Vanda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use pets or plants during discussion • Make orchards or gardens • Cleaning activities in community areas • Walks in natural environments • Roleplay activities • Peer tutoring • Creation of academic clubs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of concept maps • Activities that involve the use of maps • Pictionary game • Use of 1 minute reflection period • Activities that integrate the independent study

DISCUSSION

Profile of the respondents according to sex. Figure 1 presents the Demographic Profile of the respondents according to Sex. It can be seen in the graph that Female respondents has the larger number which consist of One Hundred fifty-one (151) learners while the Male respondents composes of One Hundred thirty-four (134) learners with a total respondent of Two Hundred eighty-five (285). This data signifies that the students enrolled in Grade 7 year level slightly equal and further signifies that the institution is a Gender and Development compliant.

Profile of the respondents in terms of Section. Figure 2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents according to section. As illustrated by the graph it is clear that section Gumamela has the highest number of learners which consist of fifty-three (53) learners and both section Vanda and Cattleya got the lowest number of learners with thirty-nine (39) students. On the other hand, sections SSP and STVEP both with qualifying exams has the same number of students which composes of fifty-one (51) learners. This group of data dramatically vary based on the enrolment processes including General Average of the students, reading assessment, qualifying exams and other.

Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 students in terms of sex. Figure 3 depicts the Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School Academic Year 2022-2023. The line graph is moderately the same in pattern based on the data. As is shown by the graph, the dominant Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 Students is “Naturalistic Intelligence” in which both Male and Female respondents got the highest percentage score of seventy-six (76%) and seventy-eight (78%) percent respectively. On the other side, “Musical Intelligence” got the lowest percentage score for Male respondents which obtained a fifty-nine percent (59%) and “Intrapersonal Intelligence” for female Respondents which obtained a fifty-eight percent (58%).

The result manifests that Grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School has more interests in activities that involves nurturing and exploring environment and other species.

The result is refuting the study of Tirri and Nokelainen (2012) which states that Naturalistic intelligence is one of the most important multiple intelligences that have to be developed, but in reality, its development is still lacking and not measured adequately in the learning process.

Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 students in terms of Section. Figure 4 illustrates the Multiple Intelligences of the Grade 7 Students of Tampilisan National High School School year 2022-2023 in terms of Section. As shown in the graph the data were steadily similar within the group of variables. Generally, the Grade 7 students is diverse from each other.

As is given in the diagram, “Naturalistic Intelligence” dominates in all section except SSP. Thus, Section Daisy obtained Eighty-four percent (84%), Cattleya obtained seventy-four percent (74%), Section Gumamela got seventy-six percent (76%), STVEP obtained Eighty-one percent (81%) and Vanda got seventy-eight percent (78%). While section SSP got the highest percentage of seventy-six percent (76%) in “Interpersonal Intelligence”.

The data declares that most of the grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School were interested in classes and activities with more involvement with surroundings and environment.

Apart from that, “Musical Intelligence” got the lowest percentage score in both section Daisy and Cattleya which obtained sixty-four percent (64%) and fifty-three percent (53%) respectively, while “Visual/Spatial Intelligence” ranked as lowest in both section Gumamela and Vanda which obtained fifty-eight percent (58%) and sixty percent (60%) and “Intrapersonal Intelligence” ranked as lowest also in both section SSP and STVEP with a percentage score of fifty-six percent (56%) and fifty-five percent (55%) respectively.

This result concludes that individual is unique and differs from each other. Learners have their own strengths, weaknesses, interests, and motivational needs that classroom facilitator must look into. In addition, teacher facilitators should be aware on the behaviour and intelligences of the learners to prepare and deliver teaching and learning process that is conformable to the interests and needs of the learners.

Further, this result corroborates the study of Gardner (2006) cited by Ahvan and Pour (2016,2) individuals are truly human beings due to the Multiple Intelligences. Each has a unique profile of intelligences of varying strengths. Although no intelligence was considered to be superior to other types. Thus, all intelligence is required for an individual, in order to participate, act purposefully and creatively in the society.

Moreover, this result is consonance to the study of Kubat (2018,1) that says Teachers must be aware of aspects such as physical traits, intelligence, perception, gender, ability, and learning styles, which are individual variances among students. By taking into account the students' unique variations, an effective and productive learning-teaching process may be planned.

Suggested Differentiated Activities. Table 1 presents the suggested differentiated activities to be used in a teaching process. The table composes of three (3) columns; the first (1) column is the section of Grade 7 learners, second (2) column indicates the “Strong Activities” based on the highest three dominant multiple intelligences. These activities are highly “recommended” in all

subject areas to align with the learners' differences and interests. On the other hand, the third (3) column consist of "Weak Activities" based on the lowest Multiple Intelligences. These activities are gently "discouraged" in all subject areas.

CONCLUSIONS

After presenting and analyzing the data, it is safe to conclude the following statements. (1) Grade 7 students of Tampilisan National High School were different in Multiple Intelligences. (2) Most of the Grade 7 students were interested in classes and activities with more involvement with surroundings and environment. (3) Musical, Visual/Spatial and Intrapersonal Intelligences were considered as weak intelligences of the respondents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the other hand, based on the result of the study, the following are highly recommended; (1) Classroom Facilitator should prepare activities based on the intelligences of the learners. (2) Classroom Facilitator are discouraged to prepare activities based on the weak multiple intelligences of the learners such as Musical, Visual/Spatial and Intrapersonal. (3) It is also recommended to use determine first the interest, strength and intelligences before administering classroom activities. (4) Make this study as reference to the future researchers with the same concept in different school to align classroom activities to the needs of the learners.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This study complied to the ethical standards of research. An Approval letter was submitted to the School principal, Grade level Coordinator in gathering data. Aside from that a letter of consent was also given to the respondents prior to the administration of the questionnaire. Thus, all gathered data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

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